

USING THE COMPARATIVE METHOD IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' LITERARY-SPEAKING COMPETENCES IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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Abstract. This article explores the pedagogical potential of the comparative analysis method in literature classes. It examines its role in developing students' critical thinking, interpretive skills, and literary competence. The study also reviews foreign scholars' contributions to comparative literary pedagogy and provides examples of tasks based on comparative analysis. The findings suggest that this method enhances students' analytical abilities and deepens their understanding of literary texts.

Keywords: The method of comparison, literature teaching, critical thinking, literary competence, methodology, pedagogy.

Introduction. In modern educational contexts, teaching literature requires innovative approaches that foster students' active engagement and higher-order thinking skills. One such approach is the comparative analysis method, which involves examining two or more literary texts to identify similarities, differences, and underlying themes¹. This method not only enriches students' understanding of literary works but also develops their analytical and interpretive abilities.

Comparative analysis is the knowledge of phenomena in existence and is one of the stages of the methodology for change. Comparison methodology of various processes existing in a specific space and time forms the basis for comparison. Therefore, there is a need to determine the place of comparative analysis in the methodology.

The use of the comparative analysis method in literature lessons develops students' skills in free expression of their opinions and critical thinking when analyzing and evaluating a literary text. By comparing the themes, ideas, and characters of works of art, students develop skills to understand the author's intent

and the content of the work of art. Also, with the help of comparative analysis, students develop communicative skills and literary-speech competencies.

. The method of comparison is a method based on the systematic comparison of philological phenomena, primarily aimed at revealing distinctive features. Therefore, in linguistics, it is called by a different name - the contrastive method. Although the theoretical foundations have not been developed, works aimed at comparing various philological phenomena have been created since ancient times. Alisher Navoi's work "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn", which focuses on the discussion of Persian and Turkic languages, is a vivid example of the method of comparison. In science, the theoretical foundations of this method were developed by the linguist I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay in the 19th century. Scientists such as Y.D.Polivanov, L.V.Sherba, S.I.Bernstein, A.A.Reformatsky, and Sh.Balli continued their scientific work in this direction.

According to the scientific conclusions of the linguist R.Rasulov, the method of comparison is a method of comparing two or more related or unrelated languages, language phenomena, and according to this feature differs from the comparative-historical method, which compares and compares only related languages. Also, unlike the comparative-historical method, it does not pay attention to the history of the languages being compared, their origin - genetic aspects, development, and does not rely on them.

It is possible to study the poetics of each element that serves the composition of a work of art and conduct scientific research on this basis. For example, Russian scholars D.S.Likhachev studied the poetics of Old Russian literature, I.V.Silantev studied the poetics of motifs, V.V.Vinogradov studied plot and style, N.E.Falikova studied the chronotope, N.Bandurina and Z.Suvanov studied images, Y.Solijonov studied artistic speech, and K.Khamraev studied the poetics of composition, and important scientific and theoretical conclusions were drawn. The fundamental monograph of O.M.Freidenber provides significant theoretical material, especially for scholars who wish to study the plot and typology of genres. The way of thinking and research skills of literary scholars can also be studied from the point of view of poetics. For example, the Russian scientist O.Presnyakov studied the poetics of the scientific work of the theoretical scientist A.A. Potebnya.

After N.Veselovsky, the methodological aspects of literary comparative studies were studied by such scholars as V.M.Zhirmunsky, A.Dima, D.Dyurishin, N.I.Konrad, I.G.Neupokoeva, M.B.Krapchenko, A.Kokorin, M.Bogatkina, V.R.Amineva, Y.I.Mineralov, and this process continues in world literature.

It is advisable to pay attention to the following thoughts of Professor K.Yuldashev: “The comparison carried out in the course of educational analysis serves the growth of students' thinking and feelings in the process of educational analysis only when, on the one hand, it is aimed at a deeper understanding of the life-aesthetic essence of the compared literary phenomena, and on the other hand, at understanding the reason for their similarity and difference”.

Adherence to didactic principles in organizing literature lessons, along with the use of various teaching methods, is one of the important tools for achieving effective educational results. In the book “Methodology of Teaching Literature” by K.Yuldashov, S.Matchonov, and T.Matyakubova, methodological recommendations are provided for teaching ways to use effective teaching methods and techniques in the teaching process, revealing aspects that have a positive impact on the student's spirituality in the analysis of a work of art, and guiding them toward the ability to use it purposefully, as well as organizing exercises for speech development. In the textbook “Methodology of Teaching Literature” created by B. Tukhliev, it is stated that the development of students' oral and written speech is one of the main tasks of the literature subject studied at various stages of education, and the speech of students is enriched and smoothed during the reading of a work of art.

. In the course of the research, the comparative method was also used in the study of Abai's poems in the 6th grade literature textbook “In my early years, I failed to chase after knowledge” and Avaz Otar's “Mastery of languages breathes life into every human being”. The method of comparison is a method aimed at identifying their common and different aspects by comparing two or more works of art. This method serves to develop students' thinking, teach them to think independently and logically, and develop their speech competence.

Through the comparison method, students gain a deep understanding of the content of a work of art, analyze the ideological views of the authors, and learn to justify their thoughts. This method is especially effective when studying works that are close in content.

During the experimental teaching process, the comparative method was implemented in teaching Abay's poem "In my early years, I failed to chase after knowledge" and Avaz Otar's poem "Mastery of languages breathes life into every human being" through the following stages:

Preparatory Stage.

The teacher reads both poems expressively to the students and forms their initial understanding.

Analytical Stage.

Students analyze each poem separately: identifying the content, main idea, and key images.

Comparative Stage.

Students are given the following tasks:

Identify the common idea of the poems.

Compare the authors' attitudes toward knowledge and learning.

Which poem impressed you more and why?

Fill in Table 1 based on the text and content of the poem.

Characteristics of Abai's poetry	Characteristic features of Avaz Otar's poetry	Characteristics of both poems

The generalization stage. Students state their conclusions and come to a common opinion about the importance of acquiring knowledge.

Questions and assignments play an important role in the comparison method. In the research work of M.Mirkosimova, it is emphasized that when analyzing works of various genres, the questions and tasks presented in the textbook should be aimed at understanding the integrity of the form elements of the artistic work in harmony with the content. In the research work of K.Khusanbaeva, questions and assignments are explained as the main tool for asking homework. In our opinion, the views of both scholars are correct, as it has been observed that the use of questions and assignments both during lessons and during homework checks yields effective results in the practical process.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the use of the comparison method in developing students' literary and speech competencies in literature lessons is considered one of the effective pedagogical approaches. This method develops students' independent thinking skills by understanding, analyzing, and identifying similarities and differences in the content of a literary text.

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